

ENHANCEMENT OF THRUST VIA FLOW ANALYSIS USING SUPERSONIC NOZZLE WITH CFD SIMULATION

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ABSTRACT – The optimization study of a convergent-divergent nozzle has been conducted to investigate the behavior of supersonic flow through it at various divergent angles and different throat-to-inlet diameter ratios. The k-ε model was employed for flow analysis, with boundary conditions set based on available experimental data. Mach number exhibits an increasing trend with rising divergent angles, leading to the identification of an optimal divergent angle. Additionally, the throat diameter to inlet diameter ratio was varied to perform further analysis. Geometry optimization was based on Mach number trends, with additional analysis conducted at different altitudes. The modeling and meshing were carried out using ICEM CFD, while CFX was utilized for solving the equations.

Keywords—Supersonic Nozzle, Mach number, CFD, k-ε model.

1. INTRODUCTION

A nozzle is a device designed to alter the characteristics of fluid flow, particularly by increasing velocity, as it exits an enclosed cavity through an orifice. Typically, a nozzle takes the form of a pipe or tube with a varying cross-sectional area, allowing it to direct or modify the flow of a fluid, whether liquid or gas. Nozzles are commonly employed to control the rate, speed, direction, mass, shape, and/or pressure of the stream that emanates from them. The primary objective of a nozzle is to enhance the kinetic energy of the flowing medium at the expense of its pressure and internal energy. Nozzles can be categorized as convergent (narrowing from a wide diameter to a smaller one in the direction of flow) or divergent (expanding from a smaller diameter to a larger one). A de Laval nozzle combines a convergent section followed by a divergent section, often referred to as a convergent-divergent nozzle.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

The concept of variable nozzle diameter was employed to calculate the geometry of CD nozzles. Different values of the ratio D^*/D_0 (0.7, 0.6, 0.5, 0.4, 0.3) were considered, along with various divergence angles of 4, 7, 10, and 13 degrees. Among these configurations, the one yielding the highest Mach number was selected for further analysis at different altitudes (in feet). It's important to highlight that the variation in area ratio was designed to ensure compliance with the choked condition, where the Mach number reaches 1 at the throat. The simulation of fluid and thermal flows through the nozzles was conducted using a computational fluid dynamics software package. ANSYS ICEM-CFD was utilized for mesh generation, while ANSYS CFX was employed for flow analysis. The turbulence models K-ε were utilized for the analysis, and the results were obtained through CFD-POST.

Boundary Condition In let Location

Total pressure =44 bar.

Total temperature = 3400k

Medium intensity = 5%

Wall=smooth

Nozzle dimensions (reference paper) In let diameter(D)=1m

Exit diameter (D0) =0.861m Mass flow rate=826 kg/sec Convergent length=0.64m

D*= throat diameter

Fig: 1. CFD analysis framework

Geometry Model(4⁰k-ε)D*/D=0.3

Fig.2 Meshing for Geometry Model

ANSYS ICEM is used to build a 3D geometry for CFD analysis is shown in fig 2 The geometry is created and Meshed. Here I am using ANSYS ICEM CFD tool to create the nozzle geometry.

Figure 3 Machnumber Plane Geometry

It is clear that Mach number at throat is 1 which satisfies maximum discharge and based on outlet Mach number thrust is calculated. From above figure it is clear that in convergent part Mach number is subsonic ($M < 1$), at throat it is sonic ($M = 1$) and at divergent it is supersonic ($M > 1$).

Geometry Model ($10^\circ k-\epsilon$) $D^*/D=0.3$

Figure 4 Mach number geometry

it is clear that Mach number at throat is 1 which satisfies maximum discharge and based on outlet Mach number thrust is calculated. From above figure it is clear that in convergent part Mach number is subsonic ($M < 1$), at throat it is sonic ($M = 1$) and at divergent it is supersonic ($M > 1$).

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Identify the optimal designs of converging-diverging nozzles that perform at maximum uniformity of thermodynamic and flow-field properties with respect to their average values at the nozzle exit. Fourteen nozzles with different divergence angle and throat to that of inlet diameter ratio were numerically investigated. In order to solve this multi-objective design optimization problem, the parameters defining the shape of the nozzle were used as design variables. After optimizing 10° and $d^*/d_0=0.3$ from above analysis it has been chosen for analysis at different altitude.

CFD RESULTS FOR VARIOUS ALTITUDES

Fig. 5 Mach number for 10000ft

Fig 6. Mach number for 20000ft

Fig.7 Mach number for 40000ft

Fig. 8 Mach number for 50000, 55000, 60000, 65000ft

From above figures it is clear that Mach number at throat is 1 which satisfies maximum discharge and based on outlet Mach number thrust is calculated. From above figure it is clear that in convergent part Mach number is subsonic ($M < 1$), at throat it is sonic ($M = 1$) and at divergent it is supersonic ($M > 1$).

Table 1: Tabulation for CFD results

Divergence angle	D*/D	VELOCITY AT OUTLET(m/s)	MACH NO	THRUST (KN)
4	0.3	2600	2.25	2147.60
	0.4	2430	2.1	2007.18
	0.5	2000	1.9	1652.00
	0.6	1900	1.65	1569.40
7	0.3	2550	2.24	2106.30
	0.4	2500	2.1	2065.00
	0.5	2100	1.8	1734.60
	0.6	1800	1.7	1486.80
10	0.3	2650	2.26	2188.90
	0.4	2350	2	1941.10
	0.5	2050	1.75	1693.30
13	0.3	2500	2.2	2065.00
	0.4	2300	2	1899.80
	0.5	1900	1.7	1569.40

Theoretical calculation of Mach number

$$M = \frac{v}{c} = \frac{v}{\sqrt{\gamma RT}}$$

$$C = \sqrt{\gamma RT} = \sqrt{0.4 \times 0.2817 \times T \times 1000}$$

$$P^* = P_0 \left(\frac{2}{\gamma + 1}\right)^{\frac{\gamma}{\gamma - 1}} = 44 \left(\frac{2}{1.4 + 1}\right)^{1.4/1.4 - 1}$$

$$P^* = 41.27 \text{ bar,}$$

$$T^*/T_0 = \left(\frac{P^*}{P_0}\right)^{\frac{\gamma - 1}{\gamma}} \quad T^* = 4300 \left(\frac{41.27}{44}\right)^{1.4 - 1/1.4}$$

$$T^* = 3338.34 \text{ K,}$$

$$C = \sqrt{1.4 \times 0.287 \times 3338.34 \times 1000}$$

$$C = 1158.617 \text{ m/s,}$$

$$M = \frac{v}{c} \quad v \text{ from fig. 6.1(g) Mach number plane Geometry for Model-1}$$

$$M = \frac{\text{V from fig}}{\text{C from calculation}}$$

$$M = 1151/1158.164 = 0.9938 \cong 1$$

$$M = 1$$

Mach number from CFD Simulation as shown in fig: 5.2(e) is validated from the above theoretical calculation.

Comparison of Mach number for theoretical and simulation is given in below Table. 5.23 And variation of Mach number is 0.9% is observed.

TABLE 2: Theoretical calculation of Mach number

parameter	Theoretical	Simulation	Difference (%)
Mach number	0.9938	1	0.9%

Table 3: Tabulation of Mach number and Velocity for various altitudes

ALTITUDE (ft.)	MACH No	VELOCITY (m/s)
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10000	2.293	2681
20000	2.332	2726
25000	2.340	2735
30000	2.344	2739
35000	2.345	2741
40000	2.346	2742
50000	2.347	2743
55000	2.347	2743
60000	2.347	2743
65000	2.347	2743

Variations of Altitude with Velocity

Fig.9 variations of Altitude with Velocity

From above Fig.9 it is evident that the altitude reaches the saturation level at 45000ft where velocity remains same.

4. CONCLUSION

This research aimed to identify the optimal designs of converging-diverging nozzles that perform at maximum uniformity of thermodynamic and flow-field properties with respect to their average values at the nozzle exit. In order to solve this multi-objective design optimization problem, the parameters defining the shape of the nozzle were used as design variables. This work showed how the variation of such parameters influenced the nozzle exit flow no uniformity.

Initially, 14 simulations were run. The steps followed to find the solutions were as follows:

Static pressure shows linear variation for different parameters like Mach number, Thrust and velocity.

- As the altitude increase the parameters shows linear progression thus at 45000ft the parameters reaches saturation level and remains constant.
- Working fluid shows linear expansion after reaching maximum trust is 2188.90 KN
- The results of 3-Dcomputational fluid dynamics are validated using theoretical calculations which indicate a very close match in the order of 0.9% which proves considerable validation.
- Generation of the computational mesh using a grid generator software package ANSYS ICEM-CFD.
- Simulations of the flow-fields and thermal analysis were run in the CFD Software package ANSYS CFX for the 14 shapes, using k-ε turbulence models with a total of 14 simulations.
- The standard deviations of the pressure, Mach number and velocity results at the exit of the nozzles were calculated.
- After the above process, thrust has been calculated.

- It has been observed that Mach number and velocity at the outlet is more for divergence angle 10° k- ϵ model with $D^*/D=0.3$
- As the divergence angle is increased with increase in the ratio of D^*/D , the divergent length will decrease and Mach number at exit will be decreased.
- From the simulation it has been observed that divergence angle 4° with $D^*/D=0.7$, divergence angle 7° with $D^*/D=0.7$, divergence angle 10° with $D^*/D=0.6$ & 0.7 , and divergence angle 13° with $D^*/D=0.6$ & 0.7 , the divergent length is less than convergent length so that expansion process is terminated due to back flow. Hence analysis is not carried out.
- Finally based on higher Mach number and velocity at the outlet, the divergence angle 10° k- ϵ with $D^*/D=0.3$ model has been optimized, the maximum thrust 2188.90 KN is obtained
- Further analysis has been carried out at higher altitude. Where we found that saturation level has been reached where Mach number and velocity was constant between 55000ft to 65000ft.
- As compared with reference paper 12.3% of enhancement of thrust obtained.

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